

Isolation of Aurantiamide Acetate from *Ageratum conyzoids*

N. SUR, R. POI, A. BHATTACHARYYA* and N. ADITYACHOUHURY

Department of Agricultural Chemistry & Soil Science, Bidhan Chandra Krishi Viswavidyalaya, Kalyani-741 235

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Plants belonging to the genus *Ageratum* (family : Compositae) elaborates several types of compounds¹. *Ageratum conyzoides* possesses remarkable insecticidal property². We report here phytochemical investigation of *Ageratum conyzoides*.

The whole plant (~5 kg) was air-dried, ground and extracted in a Soxhlet apparatus with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) for 30 h. The concentrated extract on column chromatography over silica gel, afforded a colourless crystalline compound from benzene-ethyl acetate (9 : 1) fraction. It was identified as aurantiamide acetate, m.p. 184–85°, C₂₇H₂₈N₂O₄; M⁺ 444; v_{max} 3320, 1660 (CONH), 1602, 1580, 745, 695 (Ph), 1725 (OAc), 1260 cm⁻¹ (COCH₃). All its spectral data were in agreement with those reported³ for aurantiamide acetate (1). Its identity was further confirmed by direct comparison (m.p., co-tlc, co-ir) with an authentic sample isolated from *Medicago polymorpha*⁴.

This is the first report of the occurrence of aurantiamide acetate in the genus *Ageratum*.

M.p. was determined in a sulphuric acid bath and are uncorrected. Ir spectrum (KBr) was recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 1310 spectrophotometer

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